

Short name	Liability in Storage Hubs and Clusters	Long name	Liability for leakages and other disturbances in joint hubs and clusters
Geographical scope	National + International		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<p>In a storage hub CO2 from multiple different sources is being stored. In case of a leakage along a mixed capture, transport and storage chain it is somewhat unclear how to physically attribute a specific ton of CO2 to a specific source. Therefore, a clear liability regime is needed, which provides for rules for legal attribution that fits with the monitoring practices along the value chain to provide legal clarity in such cases. While the storage provider is liable for leakage from the storage site, agreements between the storage provider and CO2 suppliers could also foresee sharing some of the corresponding financial risk, but this would have to be based on a clear attribution rule.</p>		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	<p>While the national GHG inventory accounting guidelines are clear that leakage emissions are to be reported by the country in which the leak occurs, the legal liability might be less clear, should the country have legislation in place to hold the operator to account in a cases of leakage events – especially at intersections in the CCUS chain, where liability might not be clearly attributable to one single actor and where the CO2 stream already stems from multiple sources.</p> <p>Does the storage provider (e.g. Northern Lights) and/or jurisdiction (e.g. Norway) take full responsibility for leakage (or only if all entities are Norwegian?)</p>		
Other issues this affects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Accounting Readiness - Liability - MRV Readiness - bilateral agreements 		
Reference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Havercroft, I.; Macrory, R (2014): Legal liability and carbon capture and storage • International Energy Agency (2022): Legal and Regulatory Frameworks for CCUS 		